

LINGUISTIC FEATURES OF ECONOMIC ADVERTISEMENTS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13188225>

Abstract: This article explores the linguistic features of economic advertisements in both English and Uzbek languages. Advertising is a crucial part of any economy, serving as a means for companies to communicate with their customers and promote their products and services. The article discusses various aspects of advertising, including language choice, register, persuasive language, cultural references, and clarity and simplicity, highlighting the differences between English and Uzbek economic advertisements. While both languages aim to persuade customers to make purchases, differences in language choice, persuasive techniques, cultural references, and simplicity reflect the unique characteristics of each language and culture. Understanding these linguistic features is essential for advertisers to effectively communicate their message and appeal to their target audience in both English and Uzbek markets.

Keywords: economic advertisements, persuasive language, cultural, language choice, clarity, target audience.

1 INTRODUCTION

Advertising is an essential part of any economy. It means through which companies communicate with their customers, informing them about products and services. Advertising is a concept at the intersection of several fields, such as economics, linguistics, psychology and linguoculturology, sociology; it has been given different definitions by researchers. Etymologically, according to the online dictionary Merriam Webster, the term «advertising» is derived from the Latin word «advertere», «vertere» is its core and means to draw attention or attention.[1] In addition, the word advertising in English is “advertising /ˌædvərˈtaɪzment / Brit /adˈænd:təsmənt” (Britannica Concise Encyclopedia) is pronounced in two ways. To be effective, advertisements need to be crafted carefully, considering various linguistic features to appeal to the target audience. In this article, we will explore the linguistic features of economic advertisements in both English and Uzbek languages.

According to British linguist Jeffrey Lich, the most common and important type of advertising is “consumer commercial advertising”, which is targeted advertising to the public in order to promote the sale of a commercial product or service. [2] In the UK, large sums of money are allocated for advertising, high professional skills and space for advertising. For example, L'Oréal cosmetics “Because You're Worth It” (you deserve it!); or “Washable Volumizing Mascara: This mascara delivers full volume and limitless length, featuring a formula infused with bamboo extract and fibers for long, full, lightweight lashes that don't flake or smudge. Maybelline

is the world's number 1 makeup brand, from foundation to mascara to lipstick; Diverse, on the pulse, inspired by the city and tested on its streets” (dream advertising for eyelashes). Another type of commercial advertising is «prestige advertising», where the company's name and positive image are advertised, not the product or service.

For example: “FIFA's sponsors and partners enjoy the exclusive right to display their brand name on the LED boards in the stadiums during the World Cup matches. Many TV viewers are puzzled over names like Wanda, Hisense, and Mengniu. So who are Adidas, Coca-Cola, Visa, Hyundai / Kia, Gazprom, Qatar Airways, Wanda, McDonald's, Budweiser, Hisense, Mengniu, and Vivo? ISPO.com provides an overview.”; or “The America's Cup: the oldest and most coveted trophy in the world of sailing. Its organizers have entrusted once again the vital timing of the races to Omega, a corporation whose experience in watching making and sports timekeeping dates back over 150 years... to the very origins of the America's Cup itself.” (“The America's Cup: the oldest and most achievable trophy in the world of rowing. Its organizers once again entrust Omega Corporation with scheduling race times. The corporation has more than one hundred and fifty years of experience in making and calculating race times. was formed fifty years ago.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

Language choice is crucial in advertising, as it directly influences the target audience. In English economic advertisements, the language used is often straightforward, aiming for clarity and precision.

Language choice and register are essential considerations in economic advertisements as they directly influence how the message is perceived by the target audience.

In English economic advertisements, the language used is often straightforward and concise. Advertisers aim for clarity and precision to ensure that the message is easily understood by a wide range of audiences. The register is typically informal, aiming to create a friendly and approachable tone.

Example in English: *"Get 50% off on all items! Limited time offer!"*

The use of informal language in English advertisements helps create a sense of familiarity and makes the message more relatable to the audience.

In contrast, Uzbek economic advertisements tend to use a more formal tone, often employing honorifics to show respect to the audience. The use of honorifics is deeply rooted in Uzbek culture and significantly affects the tone of advertisements.

Example in Uzbek: *"Hurmatli mijozlarimizga, barcha mahsulotlarda 50% chegirma! Chegirma muddati cheklangan!"*

The use of honorifics in Uzbek advertisements, such as "hurmatli mijozlarimizga" (dear customers), helps create a respectful and polite tone, which is highly valued in Uzbek culture.

While both English and Uzbek economic advertisements aim to attract customers, the choice of language and register differs significantly between the two languages. English advertisements tend to be more informal and direct, whereas Uzbek advertisements are often more formal and polite, reflecting the cultural norms and values of the target audience.

Understanding these differences in language choice and register is essential for advertisers to effectively communicate their message and appeal to their target audience in both English and Uzbek markets.

Persuasive language is a key component of economic advertisements in both English and Uzbek languages. Advertisers use various linguistic techniques to persuade their audience to take action and make a purchase.

English Advertisements:

In English economic advertisements, persuasive language is characterized by its directness and urgency. Advertisers often use imperative verbs, superlatives, and positive adjectives to create a sense of excitement and desirability.

Example in English: *"Don't miss out on the biggest sale of the year!"*

The use of imperative verbs such as "don't miss out" creates a sense of urgency and encourages the audience to take immediate action.

Uzbek Advertisements:

Similarly, economic advertisements in Uzbek language also use persuasive language to attract customers. However, the tone is often more formal, and the language used is characterized by its politeness and respectfulness.

Example in Uzbek: *"Yiling eng katta chegirmasini o'tkazib yubormang!"*

The use of persuasive language in Uzbek advertisements, such as "o'tkazib yubormang!" (don't miss out), is designed to create a sense of urgency while maintaining a polite and respectful tone.

While both English and Uzbek economic advertisements use persuasive language to attract customers, there are differences in tone and style. English advertisements tend to be more direct and informal, using imperative verbs and superlatives to create a sense of urgency. In contrast, Uzbek advertisements are often more formal and polite, using respectful language to persuade the audience to take action.

Understanding these differences in persuasive language is essential for advertisers to effectively communicate their message and appeal to their target audience in both English and Uzbek markets.

Cultural references play a significant role in economic advertisements, helping advertisers establish a connection with their target audience. While English and Uzbek economic advertisements share the goal of appealing to their respective audiences, the cultural references used may vary based on the cultural context of the target audience.

English Advertisements:

In English economic advertisements, cultural references may include popular trends, celebrities, or events that are relevant to the target audience. By incorporating familiar cultural elements, advertisers can create a sense of connection and relatability with their audience.

Example in English: *"Join the party and celebrate savings with us!"*

In this example, the phrase "join the party" is a cultural reference to the idea of celebration and excitement, while "celebrate savings" appeals to the audience's desire to find good deals and discounts.

Uzbek Advertisements:

Similarly, economic advertisements in Uzbek language also incorporate cultural references that resonate with the target audience. However, these cultural references are often related to local customs, traditions, and holidays that are significant to Uzbek culture.

Example in Uzbek: *"Biz bilan hamkorlik qiling va chegirmalardan foydalaning!"*

In this example, the phrase "hamkorlik qiling" (partner with us) emphasizes the importance of collaboration and partnership, which are values that are highly valued in Uzbek culture.

While both English and Uzbek economic advertisements use cultural references to appeal to their target audience, the specific references may vary based on the cultural context of the audience. English advertisements may incorporate references to popular culture or current events, while Uzbek advertisements may focus on local customs, traditions, and values that are important to the Uzbek audience.

Understanding these cultural differences is essential for advertisers to effectively communicate their message and establish a connection with their target audience in both English and Uzbek markets.

Clarity and simplicity are essential characteristics of effective economic advertisements. Both English and Uzbek economic advertisements prioritize clear and concise language to ensure that the message is easily understood by the target audience.

English Advertisements:

In English economic advertisements, simplicity is achieved through short and direct sentences. Advertisers aim to convey the message quickly and clearly, using language that is easy to understand.

Example in English: "Buy one, get one free!"

In this example, the message is simple and straightforward, clearly communicating the offer to the audience.

Uzbek Advertisements:

Similarly, economic advertisements in Uzbek language also prioritize clarity and simplicity. Sentences are often short and to the point, making it easy for the audience to understand the message quickly.

Example in Uzbek: "Birini sotib oling, birini bepul oling!"

In this example, the message is presented in a clear and concise manner, making it easy for the audience to understand the offer.

While both English and Uzbek economic advertisements prioritize clarity and simplicity, there may be differences in the specific linguistic features used to achieve this goal. English advertisements tend to use shorter sentences and direct language, while Uzbek advertisements may incorporate polite expressions and honorifics to maintain a respectful tone.

Understanding these differences in clarity and simplicity is essential for advertisers to effectively communicate their message and appeal to their target audience in both English and Uzbek markets.

3 CONCLUSION

In conclusion, advertising is an essential part of any economy, serving as a means for companies to communicate with their customers and promote products and services. Effective advertising requires careful consideration of linguistic features to appeal to the target audience. In this article, we explored the linguistic features of economic advertisements in both English and Uzbek languages.

English economic advertisements prioritize clarity, precision, and simplicity, using straightforward language to ensure the message is easily understood by a wide audience. The tone is typically informal, creating a friendly and approachable atmosphere. Persuasive language is characterized by directness and urgency, aiming to create excitement and desirability among the audience. Cultural references often include popular trends, celebrities, or events relevant to the target audience.

On the other hand, Uzbek economic advertisements tend to use a more formal tone, incorporating honorifics to show respect to the audience. The language is polite and respectful, reflecting cultural norms and values. Persuasive language is also used to attract customers, but with a more formal and polite tone. Cultural references focus on local customs, traditions, and values significant to the Uzbek audience.

Despite these differences, both English and Uzbek economic advertisements prioritize clarity, simplicity, and persuasive language to effectively communicate with their target audience. Understanding these linguistic and cultural differences is essential for advertisers to successfully appeal to their target audience in both English and Uzbek markets, ensuring their message is understood and well-received.

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